

**Synthesis of some 1,2,4-Triazino[4,3-*a*]-
indole Derivatives**

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*Manuscript received 10 May 1991, revised 26 September 1991,
accepted 7 November 1991*

IN continuation of our studies, we report here the synthesis of some 1,2,4-triazinoindoles through alkylation followed by hydrazinolysis of 3-imino/hydrazinoindol-2(1*H*)-ones.

The indole derivatives (**1a-c**) were synthesised by reacting isatin with cyanamide, 1-aminoanthraquinone and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine respectively. Compound **1a** when refluxed with 50% HCl

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gave 3-iminoindol-2(1*H*)-one (1*d*), while on treatment with hydrazine hydrate in cold it gave the aminoguanidine derivative (1*e*). Also, cyclocondensation of compound 1*e* with absolute ethanol-fused sodium sulphate produced 3-amino-1,2,4-triazino[6,5-*b*]indole (2). A similar treatment of 1*e* with glacial acetic acid-fused sodium acetate¹ led to the direct formation of acetamido derivative (3).

Reaction of 1*a* with phenacyl bromide in the presence of DMF give the corresponding *N*¹-alkyl derivative (1*f*) which by reacting with hydrazine gave 1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*a*]indole derivative (4*a*).

1*a*; R¹=H, R²=CN

b; R¹=H, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

c; R¹=H, R²=NHC₆H₄(NO₂)₂-2,4

d; R¹=R²=H

e; R¹=H, R²=C(=NH)NHNH₂

f; R¹=CH₂COPh, R²=CN

g; R¹=CH₂CO₂Et, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

h; R¹=CH₂COCH₃, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

i; R¹=CH₂COPh, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

j; R¹=CH₂CONH₂, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

k; R¹=CH₂CH₂Br, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

2; R=H
3; R=Ac

4*a*; R¹=Ph, R²=CN

b; R¹=OH, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

c; R¹=Me, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

d; R¹=Ph, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

5*a*; R¹=OH, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

b; R¹=Me, R²=C₆H₅COC₂H₄CO

Alkylation of 3-iminoindol-2(1*H*)-one (1*b*) with alkylating agents, such as ethyl bromoacetate, chloroacetone, phenacyl bromide, chloroacetamide and 1,2-dibromoethane in the presence of DMF², gave the corresponding *N*-alkyl derivatives (1*g*-*k*). Compounds 1*g*, 1, *i* on heating with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol afforded the fused triazinoindoles (4*b*, ketoform), 4*c* and 4*d* respectively. The presence of active methylene in 4*b* and 4*c* has been proved by formation the corresponding arylidene derivatives (5) by reacting with *p*-bromobenzaldehyde in the presence of glacial acetic acid-fused sodium acetate³. Also, the structure of 4*b* was finally established by direct comparison (m.m.p.) with an authentic sample prepared by the reaction of 1*j* with hydrazine hydrate followed by refluxing with 50% HCl. This reaction involves hydrolysis of the amide function followed by cyclocondensation^{4,5}.

Compound 1*k* when treated with excess hydrazine hydrate in cold followed by refluxing gave the tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*a*]indole derivative (7), while when this reaction was carried out in equivalent molar amounts, the product was bis-compound (8) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

NOTES

Alkylation of 3-hydrazinoindol-2(1*H*)-one (**1c**)^b using excess ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of DMF gave the *N*-alkyl derivative (**9**) which on refluxing with excess hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol, led to the formation of dihydro-1,2,4-triazino[4,3-*a*]indole (**10**), which on condensation with anisaldehyde in absolute ethanol gave the condensation product **11**. Finally, the treatment of compound **11** with ethanol-piperidine¹ resulted in the formation of the spiro compound (**12**).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer SP 1430 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a JNM PMX 60 spectrometer.

The physical and spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

3-Iminoindol-2(1*H*)-ones (1a-c): A mixture of isatin (0.01 mol) and appropriate amines (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solids were crystallised.

Formation of 1d: A hot solution of **1a** (5 g) in HCl (50 ml; 50%) was refluxed for 2 h and then basified with aqueous ammonia. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and crystallised.

Formation of aminoguanidone (1e): A suspension of **1a** (0.01 mol) in hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was allowed to cool for 5 min and the resulting solid was crystallised.

Cyclocondensation of 1e:

3-Amino-1,2,4-triazino[6,5-*b*]indole (2): A mixture of **1e** (0.01 mol) and fused sodium sulphate (10 g) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then filtered while hot and concentrated. The resulting solid after cooling was crystallised.

3-Acctamido-1,2,4-triazino[6,5-*b*]indole (3): A mixture of **1e** (0.01 mol) and fused sodium acetate (20 g) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled, diluted with cold water and the resulting solid was recrystallised.

Formation of 1f, k: A mixture of **1a** or **1b** (0.01 mol) and appropriate alkylating agent (0.01 mol) in DMF (100 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solids were washed with cold water and crystallised.

Formation of 4a-d: A mixture of **1f, g, h** or **i** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled, poured onto ice and the resulting solid was crystallised.

The arylidene derivatives (5a, b): A mixture of **4b** or **c** (0.01 mol) and *p*-bromobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in the presence of glacial acetic acid (100 ml) and fused sodium acetate (10 g) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled, diluted with cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1-12)*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ (ppm)
1a	195 ^a	85	3 400 (OH), 3 200-3 100 (NH), 2 280 (CN), 1 720 (CO)	
1b	170 ^b	80	3 485 (OH), 3 355-3 200 (NH), 1 750-1 700, 1 695 (CO)	
1d	~300 ^a	55	3 500-3 000br (OH, NH), 1 700 (CO)	
1e	240 ^b	90	3 400 (OH), 3 200-3 100br, (NH ₂ , NH), 1 690 (CO)	
1f	130 ^c	65	—	
1g	218 ^d	60	3 400 (OH), 1 710, 1 680-1 650 (C=O); 0.4 (3H, m, CH ₃), 2.5-2.7 (2H, m, CH ₂) 5.2 (1H, s, OH), 7.0-7.2 (4H, m, benzo) and 7.6-7.8 (7H, m, ArH)	
1h	224 ^b	70	3 440 (OH), 3 385 (OH), 1 750-1 720, 1 700-1 690 (C=O); 2.5 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.4 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.0-7.7 (3H, m, benzo), 7.8 (7H, m, ArH)	
1i	142 ^b	65	—	
1j	230 ^c	50	3 450 (OH), 3 350 (NH ₂), 1 710 (CO), 1 690-1 660 (CO), 3.3 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.3-7.6 (4H, m, benzo), 7.8-8.3 (7H, m, ArH)	
1k	240 ^b	60	—	
2	245 ^b	65	3 400 (NH ₂), 3 300-3 100 (NH)	
3	228 ^b	60	3 400 (OH), 3 200-3 100 (NH), 1 650 (CONH)	
4a	175 ^c	55	3.4 (1H, s, CH), 7.2-7.5 (5H, m, Ph), 7.8-8.0 (4H, m, ArH), 8.2 (2s, NH)	
4b	235 ^b	55	3 400 (OH), 3 200 (NH), 1 720, 1 680, 1 660 (C=O), 2.6 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.4-7.7 (4H, m, benzo), 7.8-8.0 (7H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, NH)	
4c	236 ^b	65	3 300 (NH), 1 700, 1 670 (CO); 2.5 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.3 (1H, s, CH=C), 7.3-7.6 (4H, m, benzo), 7.8-8.1 (7H, m, ArH)	
4d	228 ^b	70	—	
5a	~295 ^c	75	3 200-3 100 (OH, NH), 1 700, 1 680, 1 660 (C=O), 3.5 (1H, s, CH=C), 6.0 (1H, s, OH), 7.0-7.5 (8H, m, benzo), 7.7-8.0 (7H, m, ArH)	
5b	215 ^c	55	3 000 (Ar), 1 700, 1 680 (C=O); 0.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.3 (1H, s, CH=C), 7.0-7.6 (8H, m, benzo), 7.8-8.2 (7H, m, ArH)	
6	225 ^c	50	3 450 (NH ₂), 3 300 (NH), 1 700, 1 685 (C=O), 3.3 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.3-7.6 (4H, m, benzo), 7.8-8.4 (7H, m, ArH), 10.8, 11.0 (s, NH)	
7	~300 ^c	60	3.2-3.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.0-8.0 (11H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, NH)	
8	~300 ^c	75	3 200, 3 180 (NH), 1 700, 1 680, 1 660 (C=O), 2.3-2.6, 3.3-3.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂), 6.8-7.2 (8H, m, benzo), 7.3-7.7 (14H, m, ArH), 10.7, 11.7 (s, NH)	
9	210 ^d	65	3 200 (OH), 1 760, 1 745, 1 650 (C=O); 1.0, 1.2 (6H, s, CH ₃ , CH ₃), 2.3-2.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ , CH ₂), 3.3 (4H, s, CH ₂ -CO, CH ₂ CO) 6.7-7.7 (7H, m, ArH)	
10	295 ^b	70	—	
11	284 ^b	75	—	
12	276 ^e	70	3 300 (OH), 3 100, 3 080 (NH), 0.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.4-2.6 (4H, m, CH ₂ -CH ₂), 3.3 (1H, s, CH=N), 6.3-7.7 (11H, m, ArH), 8.3, 8.6 (s)	

*All compounds gave satisfactory for C, H and N analyses **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aMeOH, ^bEtOH, ^cDMF, ^dEt₂C₆H₅, ^eAcOH

The monohydrazone (6): It was prepared following the procedure for the formation of **4**.

Action of hydrazine hydrate on 1k. Formation of 7 and 8: A mixture of **1k** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled, diluted with cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised.

A mixture of **1k** (0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was cooled for 1 h, then refluxed for 3 h, cooled, poured into ice and the resulting solid was crystallised.

The N-alkyl derivative (9): A mixture of **1c** (0.01 mol) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.02 mol) in DMF (100 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled, poured onto ice and the resulting solid was crystallised.

Formation of 10: A mixture of **9** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then concentrated, diluted with cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised.

The monohydrazone (11): A mixture of **10** (0.01 mol) and anisaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled, diluted with cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised.¹

The spiro compound (12): A mixture of **11** (0.01 mol) and ethanol-piperidine (100 : 1, v/v) was refluxed for 8 h, then concentrated and the resultant solid was crystallised.

References

1. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 548.
2. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN and Z. EL-GENDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 1072.
3. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1987, **30**, 490.
4. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1989, **32**, 240.
5. T. V. SARASWATHI and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, **25**, 2315.
6. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, M. M. FAWZY and Z. EL-GENDY, *Asian J. Chem.*, communicated.